

Teacher reports and student achievement: How sensitive are results to who is surveyed?

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Abstract

Teacher questionnaires are used in large-scale education assessments to characterise school environments and to study relationships between teacher-reported measures and student achievement. In many such assessments, however, only one or two teachers are surveyed per school, and teachers' responses are implicitly treated as representative of broader school-level conditions. This paper examines the validity of this practice by exploiting a unique dataset from township and rural schools in South Africa that includes questionnaire responses from multiple teachers within the same schools, alongside student achievement data. The analysis first documents substantial within-school heterogeneity in teacher reports across commonly used measures, including responsive leadership, accountability, and job satisfaction. Measures often interpreted as capturing shared school-level conditions exhibit pronounced dispersion within schools, with 85% of variation occurring within rather than between schools. We then use a simulation approach to assess how sensitive estimated teacher–achievement relationships are to which teacher is sampled to represent a school. Repeatedly drawing a single teacher per school and re-estimating achievement models reveals marked differences in the stability of estimated relationships across measures. For some measures, estimated associations are directionally stable but vary in statistical significance. For others, both the magnitude and sign of the estimated relationship depend heavily on teacher selection. The findings highlight an underappreciated source of uncertainty in empirical work linking teacher questionnaire data to student outcomes. Rather than questioning the value of teacher surveys, the results point to the need for greater care in interpreting teacher–achievement relationships derived from sparse teacher samples.

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1. Introduction

Teacher questionnaires are a central component of large-scale education assessments. Alongside student achievement data, these surveys collect information on teachers' qualifications, instructional practices, working conditions, and perceptions of the school environment. Such data are used in both academic research and policy discussions to shed light on teaching conditions and school environments (see for example Aldrich et al. (2025); OECD (2024)). Studies link teacher-reported measures to student achievement outcomes (Belbase and Roblee, 2025; Bleukx et al., 2024; Eryilmaz and Strietholt, 2025; Leino et al., 2022; Marôco, 2021; Paloniemi Lindström, 2026). In most large-scale education assessments, however, only one or two teachers are surveyed per school, even in settings where multiple teachers contribute to instruction within the same grade.¹ The responses of these teachers are then used to characterise aspects of instruction or working conditions and are related to achievement outcomes at the classroom or school level.

This approach rests on an implicit assumption: that the surveyed teacher is representative of the instructional environment experienced by students in that school or within an academic domain such as literacy or mathematics. Put differently, it assumes that meaningful variation in teacher reports within schools is limited, such that the choice of which teacher is surveyed does not materially affect the estimated relationship between teacher characteristics or school-level measures derived from their self-reported responses and student achievement. This assumption is rarely made explicit, yet it warrants careful scrutiny.

This paper makes use of an unusually rich dataset from township and rural schools in South Africa that combines questionnaire responses from multiple teachers within the same schools with linked student achievement data. This structure offers a rare opportunity to examine within-school variation in teacher reports while also assessing how this variation matters for estimated relationships between teacher-reported measures and student achievement. The analysis first documents the extent of within-school dispersion in teachers' responses across a range of commonly used survey measures. It then examines the implications of this

¹ Large-scale international assessments typically sample intact classes rather than all teachers within a school. For example, TIMSS and PIRLS use a two-stage sampling design in which schools are selected first and then one intact class from the target grade is randomly sampled within each participating school (Almaskut et al., 2023; Siegel and Foy, 2024). In some cases two classes may be sampled to increase the overall sample size. Consequently, teacher questionnaire data generally reflect the responses of only one (and occasionally two) teachers per school or subject area.

dispersion for standard teacher–achievement linkages by showing how estimated relationships change when different teachers are randomly selected to represent the same school. Rather than proposing alternative measures or attempting to recover a single “true” school-level measure, the aim is to assess the stability and interpretability of estimates that rely on a small number of teacher responses. This approach reflects a common feature of large-scale education assessments, where only one or two teachers per school are surveyed. By explicitly examining how estimates change under different random selections of teachers, the analysis highlights an underappreciated source of uncertainty in studies linking school-level measures derived from teacher responses to student achievement.

1.1. Teacher questionnaires in large-scale education assessments

Teacher questionnaires form a core component of major large-scale education assessments, including PIRLS, TIMSS, and PISA. Alongside student achievement tests, these surveys capture information about teachers' backgrounds, instructional practices, working conditions, and school climate. The resulting data are used to complement achievement results and to provide insight into the contexts in which teaching and learning take place (e.g. Aldrich et al. (2025); Almaskut et al. (2023); OECD (2024)). Across these assessments, teacher questionnaires typically include measures capturing aspects of the school environment such as school leadership, accountability, workload, and job satisfaction. These measures are operationalised through self-reported items that ask teachers to reflect on their experiences, perceptions, and professional environments. In both cross-country and within-country analyses, such measures are either aggregated or linked directly to student achievement outcomes (Belbase and Roblee, 2025; Bleukx et al., 2024; Eryilmaz and Strietholt, 2025; Leino et al., 2022; Marôco, 2021; Paloniemi Lindström, 2026).

In achievement models, teacher-reported measures are interpreted as meaningful indicators of the instructional or organisational environment that shapes student learning (e.g. Leino et al. (2022)). Associations between teacher reports and achievement are discussed as evidence of the role played by teacher working conditions, school climate, or leadership practices in influencing student outcomes (e.g. Bleukx et al. (2024)). Findings from such analyses are used to draw substantive conclusions about which aspects of teachers' professional environments matter for learning, and to motivate policy recommendations aimed at improving student achievement through changes to school organisation, teacher support, or professional development (e.g. Belbase and Roblee (2025); Paloniemi Lindström (2026)).

These interpretations often rest on an implicit assumption, namely that the teacher responses included in the analyses provide an accurate and representative measure of the instructional or organisational environment experienced by

students. That is, responses from one or two surveyed teachers are treated as capturing school-level measures such as leadership, school climate, or accountability, and are interpreted accordingly in achievement models. Yet the extent to which teacher reports are shared within schools – and therefore the degree to which such interpretation is warranted – is given too little attention.

Aggregating teacher survey responses to produce school-level measure implicitly treats schools as coherent organisational units characterised by shared norms, practices, and experiences. But organisational theory, as reflected in Weick's (1976) description of schools as "loosely coupled systems", draws attention to the often weak connection between formal structures, policy demands, and what happens in classrooms. Accountability systems, leadership practices, and school routines may exist on paper or at management level, but they are not necessarily experienced in the same way by all teachers. Research on teacher sensemaking develops this argument further. Teachers do not simply absorb organisational messages; they interpret them in light of their professional identities, past experiences, and day-to-day working conditions (Spillane et al., 2002; Coburn, 2001). It follows that two teachers in the same school may have very different views of accountability pressure, professional autonomy, or job satisfaction. These differences are not necessarily signs of poor measurement. They may instead reflect real differences in how the school is perceived and navigated by staff.

It follows that drawing substantive conclusions about the role of teacher working conditions or school climate in shaping student achievement based on just one or two teachers warrants far more scrutiny. One way of doing so is to investigate the stability and validity of these measures at the school level.

1.2. The present study and research questions

The present study takes a different starting point. Rather than asking whether teacher-reported measures such as leadership, accountability, or school climate "matter" for student achievement, the analysis focuses on the stability and interpretability of estimated relationships derived from teacher questionnaire data. Using a unique dataset collected from rural and township schools in South Africa that include responses from multiple teachers within the same schools, alongside student achievement data, the study examines how much teacher reports vary within schools and how this variation affects commonly estimated teacher-achievement relationships. In particular, the analysis asks how sensitive these relationships are to plausible variation in which teachers are sampled to represent a given school.

The specific research questions are as follows:

1. How sensitive are estimated relationships between teacher-reported measures and student achievement to which teacher is sampled within a school?

2. Does this sensitivity differ between teacher-specific and school-level measures?
3. What implications does this have for interpreting teacher-achievement relationships in large-scale assessments?

2. Data and methodology

2.1. Data

The analysis uses data from the Leadership for Literacy project (Wills et al., 2019), a purpose-built school survey conducted in South African primary schools, which combines detailed teacher questionnaire data with measures of student achievement. The dataset has been used in prior studies examining school leadership, management, and instructional practices (Taylor et al., 2019; Wills and Van Der Berg, 2021) but the present analysis exploits features of the data that have not previously been the focus of attention.

The sample comprises 61 public primary schools serving learners in socio-economically disadvantaged communities in three provinces² of South Africa. Within each school, data were collected from multiple teachers, through an anonymous self-administered questionnaire provided to all teaching staff. The questionnaire does ask the teacher, however, to provide an indication of the grades that they teach. Responses to this questionnaire item were used to restrict the sample to teachers who reported teaching Grades 4–6. Although teachers cannot be linked to specific learners in the data, this restriction increases the likelihood that the teacher reports reflect the instructional environment experienced by the cohort of learners whose Grade 6 literacy outcomes are analysed.

This resulted in 471 teacher observations across the sample of 61 schools. Table 1 summarises the composition of the analytic sample. Across the 61 schools, an average of 7.72 teachers per school responded to the questionnaire (range: 1–20), alongside a mean of 42.35 Grade 6 learners per school. Student achievement data was collected through standardised literacy assessments administered to all learners in Grade 6. These assessments provide achievement measures for 2,541 students across the sampled schools. In addition, student background data was collected including basic demographic characteristics and household socio-economic factors.

² Limpopo, KwaZulu-Natal and Gauteng province. These are three provinces of a total of nine provinces in South Africa.

Table 1: Sample composition at the school level

Schools (N)	Mean teacher responses per school	Minimum teacher responses per school	Maximum teacher responses per school	Mean learners per school
61	7.72	1	20	42.35

A key limitation – and a central feature of the data for this study – is that the responses cannot be not be linked back to specific teachers and therefore the students they taught directly. The rationale behind this was that anonymous responding would promote transparency among responding teachers. At best we could identify if they taught Grades 1-3 or Grades 4-6. Teacher questionnaire responses therefore cannot be matched to classroom-level achievement outcomes. Student achievement enters the analysis at the individual level, but teacher-reported measures are necessarily linked to students only through their shared school. This structure differs from that of assessments such as PIRLS or TIMSS, where achievement is linked to a specific classroom or subject teacher, but it raises a closely related interpretive issue: to what extent do teacher-reported measures capture stable, shared features of the school environment, rather than idiosyncratic characteristics of the teachers who happen to be observed?

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. Learner achievement

The outcome variable of interest is learners' performance on a standardized Grade 6 written English literacy assessment administered in October of 2017. The test measures reading comprehension through written responses to grade-appropriate texts and was administered to all sampled Grade 6 learners in the study schools. Test scores are standardized to have mean zero and unit standard deviation across the analytic sample. This measure has been used in prior work on the same dataset and provides a consistent indicator of literacy achievement across schools.

2.2.2. Teacher-reported measures

The analysis focuses on three teacher-reported measures of teachers' professional environments and working conditions: responsive leadership, vertical accountability and job satisfaction. Responsive leadership refers to the actions of a single actor or small group of actors (e.g. the principal or school management team), and is therefore a shared, school-level characteristic to which all teachers

are exposed. Vertical accountability similarly reflects practices enacted by school leadership, but these may be applied unevenly across teachers, depending on factors such as subject, grade, or individual relationships, and may therefore exhibit wider within-school variation. Job satisfaction captures teachers' own affective experiences of their work and is therefore primarily individual-level, although it may also reflect shared features of the school environment, such as working conditions or organisational climate. Focusing on this set of measures therefore allows the analysis to examine how the stability and interpretability of teacher-achievement relationships differ across measures that operate at different levels of the school environment.

(i) Responsive leadership

Teacher-reported responsive leadership is measured using four questionnaire items capturing teachers' perceptions of how school leadership and management engage with teaching staff. This set of items is closely related to dimensions of leadership discussed in the literature on relational and participatory school leadership, including responsiveness to teachers' views, consultation in decision-making, and support for teachers' work (e.g. Johnson and Brown (2025); Nguyen et al., (2026)). All items are framed from the perspective of teachers' own experiences and refer to the actions of the principal or school management. Specifically, teachers were asked:

- How much does the principal of this school listen to teachers' ideas and opinions about curriculum?
- Since you started working at this school, how much has school management guided you to improve as a teacher?
- How often does the principal consult teachers on decisions or any developments that affect them?
- How good or bad is school management at resolving conflicts with staff when they arise?

Responses are recorded on ordered categorical scales, with response options reflecting increasing degrees of listening, guidance, consultation, or effectiveness in conflict resolution. While the response scales differ slightly across items, all four questions are intended to capture teachers' perceptions of the responsiveness and engagement of school leadership. The four items are summarised into a single measure of responsive leadership using principal components analysis (PCA). The first component captures roughly 60% of the shared variation across items and is retained as the composite index. The scale shows acceptable internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = 0.75), and the resulting index is normalised to have mean zero and unit variance.

(ii) Accountability

Teacher-reported accountability is measured using three questionnaire items that capture the extent to which teachers' instructional practices are subject to monitoring and oversight within schools. These items align with strands of the literature on 'vertical' school accountability, that is, frameworks that conceptualise accountability in terms of hierarchical processes of supervision and control, including lesson observation, curriculum monitoring, and instructional management by school leadership (e.g. Ehren and Godfrey (2017); Shields et al. (2021)). The questions asked:

- How often does your HOD (i.e. head of department)³ in this school check to see how much of the curriculum you have taught?
- How often does your HOD (i.e. head of department) in this school come to your class to observe you teaching (for at least 10 minutes of a lesson)?
- How often does your principal in this school come to your class to observe you teaching (for at least 10 minutes of a lesson)?

Response options are ordinal and reflect increasing frequency of oversight, ranging from "never" to "every day", with category labels varying slightly across items. The three items are combined into a single accountability index using PCA. The first principal component explains approximately 66% of the total variance across the items and is used as the composite measure. The internal consistency of the scale is acceptable (Cronbach's alpha = 0.73). The resulting index is standardised to have mean zero and unit variance.

(iii) Job satisfaction

Teacher-reported job satisfaction is measured using four questionnaire items that capture teachers' affective orientation toward their work and their experience of the school environment. This set of items aligns with a long tradition in the literature that conceptualises job satisfaction as an individual-level evaluation of one's work, shaped by both intrinsic aspects of teaching and features of the organisational context (e.g. working conditions, leadership, and workplace climate) (Bellibaş et al., 2025; Edinger and Edinger, 2018). Teachers were asked:

- How much do you like teaching in this school?
- When you wake up on a Monday morning, how do you feel about going to work?
- How happy are you with this school's SMT?
- How stressed do you feel in this school?

Response options are ordered categorical scales, with "stress" measured on a three-category scale and the other items measured on four- or five-category scales. Together, the items capture enjoyment of teaching in the school, affect

³ A head of department (or HOD) is a middle manager in South African schools. They typically report to a Deputy principal or principal and collectively, the HODs and principals comprise a "School Management Team (SMT)".

toward going to work, satisfaction with school management, and self-reported stress at work. The four items are summarised into a single measure of job satisfaction using principal components analysis. The first component captures 58% of the common variation across responses and is retained as the index. Together, the items show acceptable internal coherence (Cronbach's alpha = 0.73). As is the case with the other two measures, the resulting measure is standardised to have mean zero and unit variance prior to analysis.

2.2.4 Descriptive patterns in teacher reports

Before turning to regression-based analyses, this section documents the extent of within-school variation in teacher questionnaire responses using simple descriptive evidence. The focus is on disagreement between teachers working in the same school and responding to the same survey items. Two complementary descriptive tools are used. First, stacked bar graphs illustrate the distribution of teacher responses within selected schools for individual questionnaire items. These figures are intended to provide an intuitive sense of how much teachers within the same school agree or disagree in their reports. Second, summary statistics (including within-school standard deviations and intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs)) are used to characterise the degree of within-school variation more systematically across the full sample and across measures.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of teacher responses within 10 schools for a single questionnaire item from the responsive leadership index: how often the principal consults teachers on decisions or developments that affect them. Each bar represents one school, with responses shown as the percentage of teachers in that school selecting each category. The ten schools were selected for illustrative purposes. Schools were randomly drawn from those with between 8 and 18 responding teachers on the relevant survey item. The figure shows there is substantial within-school disagreement in many schools, with teachers in the same school often spread across multiple response categories. For example, in several schools, teachers' responses range from "rarely" or "sometimes" to "often" or "almost always". The figure illustrates that even for a single item intended to capture a shared aspect of school management, teachers working in the same school frequently report very different experiences.

Figure 1: Within-school distribution of teacher responses to a responsive leadership questionnaire item (“How often does the principal consult teachers on decisions or developments that affect them?”)

Notes: Each bar shows the distribution of teacher responses within an individual school. Schools shown are a random subset of 10 schools with between 8 and 18 responding teachers on this item, selected to avoid unstable percentage distributions driven by small denominators.

Figure 2 presents the within-school distribution of teacher responses to the vertical accountability item asking how often the principal observes them teaching. As with Figure 1, schools are randomly drawn from those with between 8 and 18 responding teachers on the relevant survey item. The figure again reveals substantial within-school heterogeneity. In several schools, teachers' responses span a wide range of categories, from "never" to "weekly" or "daily," indicating very different reported experiences of instructional observation within the same school.

Figure 2: Within-school distribution of teacher responses to the accountability questionnaire item “How often does the principal come to your class to observe you teaching?”.

Notes: Each bar shows the distribution of teacher responses within an individual school. Schools shown are a random subset of 10 schools with between 8 and 18 responding teachers on this item, selected to avoid unstable percentage distributions driven by small denominators.

Figure 3 presents within-school distributions of teacher responses to the job satisfaction item asking how teachers feel when they wake up on a Monday morning and think about going to work for the same 10 schools as considered in the previous two figures. As with the responsive leadership and accountability items, there is substantial heterogeneity in responses among teachers working in the same school. In many schools, teachers' responses span the full range from “very unhappy” to “very happy”, indicating markedly different affective experiences of work within the same institutional setting. The figure illustrates that teachers working in the same school often report very different feelings about going to work, reinforcing the extent of heterogeneity in teacher reports observed across measures and questionnaire items.

Figure 3: Within-school distribution of teacher responses to the job satisfaction questionnaire item “When you wake up on a Monday morning, how do you feel about going to work?”.

Notes: Each bar shows the distribution of teacher responses within an individual school. Schools shown are a random subset of 10 schools with between 8 and 18 responding teachers on this item, selected to avoid unstable percentage distributions driven by small denominators.

The preceding figures illustrate within-school heterogeneity in teacher reports using specific questionnaire items. We next consider the extent of variation in each of the three measured constructs more explicitly by reporting the intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) and school-level standard deviation of each composite measure. Results are shown in Table 2. Across all three composite measures, within-school variation is substantial, indicating that teachers working in the same school often report meaningfully different experiences. Consistent with the item-level findings, this variation is not confined to measures that are inherently individual-level constructs (e.g. job satisfaction). Measures typically interpreted as reflecting shared school-level conditions (such as responsive leadership and accountability) also exhibit considerable dispersion within schools. The ICC estimates reinforce this point. For each measure, at least 85% of total variation occurs within rather than between schools, implying limited agreement among teachers in the same school. While the extent of within-school heterogeneity differs across measures, no measure displays the level of within-school consensus

that would be expected if teacher reports primarily captured stable, shared features of the school environment.

Table 2: Descriptive measures of within-school variation in teacher-reported measures

Measure	ICC	School-level standard deviation	Mean teachers per school	Min teachers per school	Max teachers per school
Responsive leadership index	0.152	0.542	10.6	1	16
Accountability index	0.129	0.560	12.5	1	20
Job satisfaction index	0.145	0.488	13.2	1	15

Notes: The table reports descriptive statistics for the three teacher-reported measures used in the analysis. The intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) indicates the share of total variation attributable to differences between schools. Two schools have only a single teacher response.

These descriptive results show that substantial within-school disagreement in teacher reports is not confined to a particular measure or type of questionnaire item. While heterogeneity in responses may be considered unsurprising for items that capture individual-level experiences (such as how teachers feel about going to work on a Monday morning) it is less expected for items intended to reflect shared features of teachers' working conditions. Yet pronounced within-school heterogeneity is visible for all three items, including those designed to capture school-level practices such as how often the principal consults teachers on decisions that affect them. This evidence shows that even aspects of the school environment that are typically interpreted as collective or shared may be experienced, or at least reported, very differently by teachers working in the same school. These descriptive patterns raise a natural question about what such heterogeneity means for empirical analyses that link measures based on the reports of a single teacher to student achievement.

2.3. Simulation design

The simulation approach is motivated by the descriptive evidence presented above, which shows substantial within-school heterogeneity in teacher reports. In settings where responses from only one or two teachers are used to characterise a school, such heterogeneity implies that estimated relationships between teacher-reported measures and student achievement may depend on which teachers happen to be sampled. The simulation is designed to assess the extent of this sensitivity directly.

The simulation proceeds by repeatedly sampling a single teacher from each school. In each iteration, one teacher is drawn at random from the set of teachers observed in a given school, and that teacher's reported values for the relevant measures are used to represent the school. This procedure mirrors the structure of many empirical applications in which a small number of teachers are surveyed per

school, while exploiting the fact that the present dataset contains responses from multiple teachers within schools. For each simulated draw, student achievement is regressed on the teacher-reported measure of interest using the same achievement specification throughout. The achievement specification is given by:

$$Y_{is} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_s + \mathbf{X}'_{is} \gamma + \mathbf{Z}'_s \delta + \theta_p + \varepsilon_{is},$$

where Y_{is} denotes standardized Grade 6 literacy achievement for learner i in school s , and T_s represents the teacher-reported measure drawn for that school in a given simulation iteration. \mathbf{X}_{is} includes learner-level controls (gender and overage status⁴), while \mathbf{Z}_s includes school-level characteristics (class size, asset index, no-fee status, and indices of infrastructure, resources, and organisation). Province fixed effects θ_p are included in all specifications. Standard errors are clustered at the school level.

The simulation is conducted 1,000 times for each measure. Because one teacher is sampled independently within each school in each iteration, the total number of possible combinations across schools far exceeds the number of teachers observed in the data. Iterations are therefore drawn with replacement across simulations, allowing the distribution of estimates to approximate the sampling variability that would arise if a single teacher were observed per school. The simulation generates a distribution of estimated coefficients rather than a single point estimate. The resulting distributions are used to examine how frequently estimated relationships change sign, attain conventional levels of statistical significance, or vary in magnitude. This allows the analysis to assess the stability of commonly estimated achievement relationships in the presence of within-school heterogeneity in teacher reports.

3. Results

Figure 4 summarises the distribution of estimated effects of responsive leadership on learner achievement across the simulation draws. Panel A shows the kernel density of the regression coefficients, while Panel B shows the corresponding distribution of t-statistics. Across simulations, the estimated coefficients are consistently positive. The distribution of point estimates is centred around a modest positive effect, with relatively little mass near zero and very few negative estimates (Panel A). This indicates that, in this dataset, randomly selecting a different teacher within the same school rarely reverses the direction of the estimated relationship between responsive leadership and achievement, although the magnitude of the estimate varies meaningfully across draws. The distribution of t-statistics in Panel B shows substantially more dispersion. While the modal t-

⁴ Learners are coded as being overage if they are two or more years older than they should be in Grade 6.

statistic lies above conventional significance thresholds, a non-trivial share of draws yield t-statistics below 1.96, implying that statistical significance is sensitive to which teacher is sampled. At the same time, some draws produce very large t-statistics, reflecting combinations of sampled teachers for whom reported responsive leadership aligns particularly strongly with learner outcomes. These results show that for responsive leadership, the estimated effect is generally positive across simulations, but inference about statistical significance is far less stable.

Figure 4: Distribution of estimated effects of responsive leadership across simulations

Notes: Panel A shows the kernel density of regression coefficients estimated across repeated simulations in which one teacher is randomly selected per school. The dashed vertical line indicates zero. Panel B shows the corresponding distribution of t-statistics, with the dashed vertical line marking the 5% two-sided significance threshold ($t = 1.96$). Each simulation estimates the same achievement model. Variation across simulations reflects sensitivity of the estimated responsive leadership–achievement relationship to which teacher is randomly selected per school.

For accountability, the simulation results reveal a markedly different pattern. Figure 5 shows the distribution of estimated coefficients and t-statistics across simulation draws. In contrast to responsive leadership, the distribution of coefficient estimates in Panel A is centred close to zero and is approximately symmetric, with substantial

mass on both positive and negative values. This indicates that the estimated accountability–achievement relationship is highly sensitive to which teacher is sampled within a school, with no stable direction of effect across simulations. The distribution of t-statistics in Panel B reinforces this instability. Most t-statistics cluster around zero, and the vast majority do not meet conventional significance thresholds. Only a small share of simulation draws produce statistically significant estimates in either direction. Together, the accountability results point to a lack of directional and inferential robustness when teacher-level accountability measures are based on a single, randomly selected teacher per school. Unlike responsive leadership, where the direction of the estimated effect is broadly stable despite variation in statistical significance, vertical accountability estimates fluctuate widely in both magnitude and sign, raising concerns about the interpretability of single-teacher estimates for this measure.

Figure 5: Distribution of estimated effects of vertical accountability across simulations

Notes: Panel A shows the kernel density of regression coefficients estimated across repeated simulations in which one teacher is randomly selected per school. The dashed vertical line indicates zero. Panel B shows the corresponding distribution of t-statistics, with the dashed vertical line marking the 5% two-sided significance threshold ($t = 1.96$). Each simulation estimates the same achievement model. Variation across simulations reflects sensitivity of the estimated accountability–achievement relationship to which teacher is randomly selected per school.

The simulation results for job satisfaction indicate a generally positive but less stable relationship with learner achievement. As shown in Figure 6, the distribution of coefficient estimates in Panel A is centred on a positive value, with the bulk of the mass lying above zero, although a non-negligible left tail extends into negative territory. This suggests that, while most simulation draws yield a positive estimated association between job satisfaction and achievement, the magnitude of the effect varies considerably depending on which teacher is sampled within a school. The distribution of t-statistics in Panel B shows that statistical significance is similarly sensitive to teacher selection. Although the modal t-statistic lies near or slightly above conventional significance thresholds, a substantial share of draws produce t-statistics below 1.96 in absolute value, indicating that statistical significance is not robust across simulations. At the same time, a subset of draws yields large positive t-statistics, reflecting cases in which sampled teachers' reported job satisfaction aligns strongly with learner outcomes.

Figure 6: Distribution of estimated effects of job satisfaction across simulations

Notes: Panel A shows the kernel density of regression coefficients estimated across repeated simulations in which one teacher is randomly selected per school. The dashed vertical line indicates zero. Panel B shows the corresponding distribution of t-statistics, with the dashed vertical line marking the 5% two-sided significance threshold ($t = 1.96$). Each simulation estimates the same achievement model. Variation across simulations reflects sensitivity of the estimated job satisfaction–achievement relationship to which teacher is randomly selected per school.

These patterns are summarised in Table 3, which facilitates direct comparison of the stability of the estimated achievement relationships across measures. Responsive leadership stands out as the most stable: 99.3% of simulation draws yield a positive coefficient, and 59.2% produce statistically significant estimates. Job satisfaction is also largely directionally stable, with 94.4% of coefficients positive, but statistical significance is achieved less frequently (36.3% of draws). Accountability shows markedly lower stability on both dimensions, with coefficients almost evenly split between positive and negative values and statistical significance observed in only 7.4% of simulations. Overall, the table highlights substantial differences across measures in how sensitive estimated relationships are to which teacher is sampled within schools, even when models and data are otherwise identical. Notably, there is no clear correspondence between achievement relationship stability and whether a measure is typically understood as operating at the school level (responsive leadership), the individual level (job satisfaction), or a combination of the two (vertical accountability).

Table 3: Stability of estimated achievement relationships across simulations

Measure	% b>0	% b<0	% significant
Responsive leadership index	0.993	0.007	0.592
Accountability index	0.554	0.446	0.074
Job satisfaction index	0.944	0.056	0.363

The table reports the share of simulation draws in which the estimated coefficient is positive (% b > 0), negative (% b < 0), and statistically significant (% t ≥ 1.96). Each simulation randomly selects one teacher per school and estimates the same achievement model on the same student sample. Differences across measures therefore reflect sensitivity of the estimated achievement relationship to teacher selection within schools, rather than differences in model specification or sample composition.

4. Discussion

This paper contributes to a growing literature that uses teacher questionnaire data from international large-scale assessments to examine associations between teacher-reported aspects of schooling and student achievement. Studies using PIRLS, TIMSS, and similar datasets have generated a substantial body of evidence linking measures such as instructional practices, professional development, accountability, and job satisfaction to student outcomes (Leino et al., 2022; Paloniemi Lindström, 2026). While this literature has been careful to acknowledge the correlational nature of these associations, results are discussed in ways that implicitly assume a stable and well-defined relationship between these measures and student achievement.

Our findings suggest that this assumption warrants closer scrutiny. By leveraging within-school variation in teacher reports and simulating the random selection of a single teacher per school, we show that estimated relationships between teacher-reported measures and achievement can be highly sensitive to which teacher happens to be observed. For some measures (most notably responsive leadership)

the estimated relationship is relatively stable across simulations. For others, particularly vertical accountability, both the sign and statistical significance of the coefficient vary substantially. Job satisfaction falls somewhere in between: the estimated relationship is more often positive than not, but still far from robust to teacher selection.

These results have direct implications for how findings from PIRLS, TIMSS, and similar assessments are interpreted and communicated. Analyses that link teacher-reported measures to student outcomes are most defensible when framed as documenting associations between sampled teacher reports and achievement, rather than as identifying effects of well-defined school-level measures. Stronger claims (particularly those that imply a stable or generalisable relationship between a teacher-reported measure and achievement) are difficult to sustain when estimates are sensitive to teacher selection within schools. Careful attention to language is therefore warranted, especially in distinguishing between individual teachers' perceptions and broader features of the instructional environment. For researchers and policymakers drawing on large-scale assessment data, the key implication is not that teacher questionnaire data should be avoided, but that estimates of the relationship between teacher-reported measures and student achievement depend considerably on how representative sampled teacher responses are of the broader instructional environment within schools.

Several limitations of the study should be noted. Firstly, the data do not permit a direct linkage between individual teachers and the specific students they teach. As a result, the analysis cannot speak to teacher-specific effects on student achievement or to heterogeneity in impacts across classrooms. The focus instead is on how teacher-reported measures are used to characterise schools or instructional environments in large-scale assessments, and on the implications of this practice when teacher reports vary within schools. Secondly, the analysis draws on data from a single country and a relatively homogenous assessment context. While the issues examined here are common to many international large-scale assessments, the extent of within-school variation in teacher reports and its implications for estimated relationships may differ across systems, survey instruments, or policy contexts. Thirdly, the simulation exercise is intended to be illustrative rather than exhaustive. The repeated random sampling of teachers is designed to highlight how sensitive estimated relationships between teacher-reported measures and student achievement are to teacher selection, not to provide a full accounting of all possible sources of uncertainty. Other design features (such as the number of teachers sampled per school, the specific measures, or alternative aggregation strategies) may also shape stability and merit further investigation.

5. Conclusion

This paper examines a common approach in research using teacher questionnaire data from large-scale assessments that implicitly treats a small number of surveyed teachers as representative of the instructional environment experienced by students within a school. Using data that include multiple teacher responses per school, we show that this approach is unwarranted, as estimated relationships between teacher-reported measures and student achievement can vary meaningfully depending on which teacher is sampled, even when models and student samples are otherwise identical. Rather than questioning the value of teacher questionnaires, the analysis points to the need for greater care in how such data are used and discussed. For researchers and policymakers alike, the key message is that teacher-reported measures drawn from sparse samples should be interpreted as conditional on who is observed, rather than as precise or fully representative indicators of school-level conditions. Making this uncertainty explicit is an important step toward more transparent and interpretable evidence on the links between teaching, school environments, and student learning.

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